

Assessment of regulatory labeling compliance of red yeast rice supplements on the Bulgarian market

Katerina Slavcheva¹

¹ Department of Organisation and Economics of Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Plovdiv, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Daniela Kafalova (daniela.kafalova@mu-plovdiv.bg)

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Abstract

Introduction: Food supplements (FSs) containing monacolins derived from red yeast rice (RYR) have become increasingly prevalent on the European Union (EU) market and are classified under Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 as “Restricted substances” and “Substances under Community scrutiny”.

Aim: This study aims to assess EU regulatory requirements for FSs containing monacolins from RYR, evaluate labeling compliance of selected FSs on the Bulgarian market, and identify common ingredient combinations in registered products.

Materials and methods: A documentary analysis of the regulatory requirements applicable to FSs containing monacolins from RYR was conducted, alongside a review of the Bulgarian register of FSs. In addition, 18 FSs containing these ingredients available on the Bulgarian market were selected, and the information provided on their packaging was compared with the relevant EU labeling requirements.

Results and discussion: RYR is most frequently combined with plant extracts, coenzyme Q10, and B vitamins. Labelling of FSs containing monacolins from RYR is required to include specific mandatory warnings, including recommendations to avoid a daily intake of 3 mg or more of monacolins. Non-compliance with labeling requirements was identified in 11 of the 18 FSs examined due to the absence of mandatory information required by national legislation or warnings mandated by EU regulations for FSs containing monacolins from RYR.

Conclusion: The results indicate that some FSs on the Bulgarian market do not comply with EU labeling requirements, highlighting the need for strengthened regulatory control.

Keywords

Food supplements, label, monacolins, red yeast rice, regulatory framework

Introduction

In the European Union (EU), food supplements (FSs) are legally defined as foodstuffs, and their regulation is established under Directive 2002/46/EC of the European

Parliament and the Council. This directive establishes a formal legal definition of FSs, provides harmonized lists of vitamins and minerals allowed for use in their manufacture, and specifies mandatory labeling requirements to ensure

consistency and consumer protection across Member States (European Food Safety Authority 2018; Hadzhieva 2023).

In Bulgaria, the regulation of FSs is implemented under the Food Act, with the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (BFSA) serving as the competent authority (Petkova 2014; Tsvetkova 2014; Republic of Bulgaria 2020). Following amendments to the Food Act in 2020, FSs may be placed on the Bulgarian market only after registration with the BFSA and inclusion in a public national register. Labeling, presentation, and advertising of FSs must comply with harmonized EU legislation, including Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011. Since 30 December 2021, the national Ordinance on Food Supplements has been in force, requiring specific information to be provided on the labeling of these products placed on the Bulgarian market (Republic of Bulgaria 2021):

- The names of the categories of nutrients or substances characterizing the product, or an indication of their nature;
- The portion of the product recommended for daily consumption;
- A warning not to exceed the recommended daily dose;
- A statement to the effect that FSs should not be used as a substitute for a varied diet;
- A statement that the product should be stored out of the reach of young children; and
- The registration number and registration date of the FS as recorded in the national register, in accordance with the Food Act.

These requirements are harmonized in accordance with Directive 2002/46/EC (European Parliament 2002).

According to Directive 2002/46/EC, FSs are defined as foodstuffs intended to supplement the normal diet and which are concentrated sources of nutrients or other substances with a nutritional or physiological effect, alone or in combination, marketed in dose form, namely, forms such as capsules, pastilles, tablets, pills, and other similar forms; sachets of powder; ampoules of liquids; drop-dispensing bottles; and other similar forms of liquids and powders designed to be taken in measured small unit quantities (European Parliament 2002). There is a wide range of nutrients and other ingredients that might be present in FSs, including vitamins, minerals, amino acids, essential fatty acids, fiber, and various plants and herbal extracts (European Parliament 2002).

However, certain plant species contain bioactive compounds that may pose health risks under specific circumstances (Ivanova 2016). Such substances include hydroxyanthracene derivatives found in *Rhamnus frangula*, *Rhamnus purshiana*, *Cassia senna*, *Rheum palmatum*, and *Rheum officinale* Baillon; (-)-epigallocatechin-3-gallate from green tea extracts; and monacolins from red yeast rice (RYR). These compounds are listed in Article 8 of Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006, specifically in Annex III, Part C, and are classified as “substances under Community scrutiny” (European Parliament 2006).

RYR is derived from the fermentation of rice (*Oryza sativa*) using yeast species, most commonly *Monascus purpureus*

(Cicero 2021), resulting in the formation of several bioactive compounds collectively known as monacolins. Among these, monacolin K is the principal active compound. Monacolin K in its lactone form has been shown to be chemically identical to lovastatin, the active pharmaceutical ingredient used in medicinal products for the treatment of hypercholesterolemia (European Commission 2022). A meta-analysis has demonstrated that FSs containing RYR significantly reduce total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), and triglyceride levels, while increasing high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) (Rahmani 2023).

On 25 June 2018, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) adopted a scientific opinion on the safety of monacolins present in RYR (EFSA Panel on Food Additives and Nutrient Sources added to Food 2018). EFSA concluded that the intake of monacolins from RYR-containing FSs may lead to exposure to monacolin K comparable to the therapeutic doses of lovastatin. Furthermore, it was established that the adverse effect profile of RYR is similar to that observed for lovastatin. According to published reports, adverse reactions have been identified affecting the musculoskeletal and connective tissue (including rhabdomyolysis), the liver, the nervous system, and the gastrointestinal tract, as well as the skin and subcutaneous tissue (European Commission 2022).

EFSA has considered that the available evidence on adverse effects in humans is sufficient to determine that monacolins present in RYR, when used in FSs, pose a health risk at a daily intake of 10 mg. Moreover, individual cases of severe adverse reactions, including rhabdomyolysis, hepatitis, and dermatological disorders leading to hospitalization, have been reported at intake levels as low as 3 mg/day of monacolins from RYR. In light of the significant adverse health effects associated with the consumption of monacolins from RYR, regulatory measures have been introduced to restrict their use at daily intake levels of 3 mg or higher (European Commission 2022). Consequently, monacolins from RYR were included in Part B, “restricted substances,” of Annex III to Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 (European Parliament 2006). In addition, Part B concerning monacolins from rice fermented with red yeast establishes specific conditions of use and labeling requirements for FSs, requiring that the daily portion of the product provide less than 3 mg of monacolins (European Commission 2022).

Given the potential for adverse health effects associated with monacolin intake and the persistence of scientific uncertainty, EFSA has placed the use of monacolins from RYR in FSs under scrutiny. Consequently, these substances have been included in Part C (“substances under Community scrutiny”) of Annex III to Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 (European Commission 2022).

The present study aimed to analyze the regulatory requirements applicable at the European level to FSs containing monacolins from RYR and to assess whether the labeling of selected FSs available on the Bulgarian market complies with these requirements. In addition, the study sought to examine FSs containing monacolins from RYR that have been registered in Bulgaria to date and to identify their most common ingredient combinations.

Materials and methods

A documentary analysis of the regulatory requirements applicable to FSs containing monacolins from RYR was conducted. The analysis was based on a review of the following legislative documents: Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006, Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011, the Bulgarian Food Act (Republic of Bulgaria 2020), and the Food Supplements Ordinance (Republic of Bulgaria 2021).

A register-based analysis was also performed using the publicly available website of the BFSa to identify FSs containing monacolins from RYR that were registered at the time of the study.

For the purpose of the study, a total of 18 FSs containing monacolins from RYR available on the Bulgarian market were collected from pharmacies, online pharmacies licensed by the Bulgarian Drug Agency, FS retailers, and online FS retailers licensed by the BFSa. The information provided on their packaging was subsequently compared with the applicable European regulatory requirements. Data collection was performed through a review of product labels and accompanying consumer information. All available data were transferred to a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet for further analysis. The extracted information included the product trade name, manufacturer, country of origin, additional active ingredients, labeled amount (mg) per maximum daily dose, recommended daily intake, pharmaceutical form, health claims, and the presence of mandatory statements and warnings.

Regulatory compliance was assessed based on the following criteria:

- Presence of mandatory information required for all FSs in accordance with applicable Bulgarian legislation and the EU regulatory framework;
- Label information, including dosage form, labeled amount per maximum daily dose, content of RYR, total monacolins, and monacolin K per maximum daily dose, as well as details on the supplier and country of origin;
- Product composition and intended use, including the presence of complete information on ingredients and specification of the product's intended purpose; and
- Presence of all mandatory warnings and statements applicable to FSs containing monacolins from RYR.

An FS was classified as "non-compliant" if it failed to satisfy even a single mandatory requirement from either the general FS labeling framework (Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011, Bulgarian Food Act, and Food Supplements Ordinance) or the specific RYR restrictions (Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006).

Results

Labeling requirements for FSs containing monacolins from RYR

A review of the relevant legislation indicates that labels of RYR-containing supplements must include specific

Labelling Requirements

Figure 1. Additional requirements for FSs containing monacolins from RYR according to Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 (created via Canva.com).

mandatory warnings, such as advising consumers against exceeding a daily intake of 3 mg of monacolins from RYR. The complete set of labeling requirements is summarized in Fig. 1. The absence of information on the specified criteria on FS packaging will be considered indicative of non-compliance with regulatory requirements.

Assessment of regulatory labeling compliance of selected RYR supplements

The register-based analysis identified a total of 138 FSs containing monacolins from RYR registered in Bulgaria, with the earliest entry dating back to 2007 and the most recent recorded in 2025. This figure represents the cumulative number of registered products, rather than current market availability, as products withdrawn or discontinued remain listed in the BFSa register.

For this study, 18 FSs containing RYR were purchased from pharmacies, licensed online pharmacies, FS retailers, and online FS retailers. The supplements were manufactured in Bulgaria ($n = 5$), Italy ($n = 4$), Poland ($n = 3$), the USA ($n = 2$), and one each in Spain, Switzerland, Belgium, and France (Table 1).

In Bulgaria, FS labeling is required by the Food Act to indicate the registration number and the date of entry in the national register. Among the analyzed FSs, five (Samples 5, 10, 13, 14, and 15) lacked the registration date, and four of these (Samples 5, 13, 14, and 15) also did not display the registration number. On one FS (Sample 2), both the registration number and date were illegible. Additionally, the Bulgarian-language label of one FS (Sample 1) did not

Table 1. Information provided on the label regarding composition, warnings, maximum daily dose, supplier, and country of origin of the analyzed FSs.

Sample no.	Ingredients declared on the label	Required information according to Bulgarian legislation ^a	Labeled amount per maximum daily dose	Dosage form	Labeled amount (mg) per maximum daily dose			Supplier	Country of origin
					RYR content declared on label per maximum daily dose (mg)	Monacolins content declared on the label per maximum daily dose (mg)	Monacolin K content declared on the label per maximum daily dose (mg)		
Sample 1	RYR, coenzyme Q10, <i>Cyclanthera pedata</i> L. Schrad. fruits, phytosterols	No The information that this FS should be stored out of the reach of young children was missing	2	Tablets	96.6	N/A	2.95	Pharmacy	Italy
Sample 2	RYR	No Registration number and date were illegible	1	Capsules	600	2.4	N/A	Online pharmacy	USA
Sample 3	RYR, black garlic extract, coenzyme Q10, policosanol, folic acid, vitamin B12	Yes	1	Capsules	58	2.9	N/A	Online pharmacy	Spain
Sample 4	RYR, fermented soybean dry extract (nattokinase), bergamot orange fruit juice dry extract (polyphenols), turmeric rhizome dry extract (curcumin)	Yes	1	Capsules	72.5	N/A	2.9	Pharmacy	Switzerland
Sample 5	RYR, dry extract of cordyceps (<i>Cordyceps sinensis</i>), inosine, acetyl-L-carnitine, magnesium oxide	No Registration number and date were missing	2	Tablets	600	N/A	Under 3 (Not specified)	Pharmacy	Bulgaria
Sample 6	Monacolins, omega 3 (DHA and EPA), <i>Cynara cardunculus</i> L., coenzyme Q10, vitamin B12, piperine, <i>Olea europaea</i> L. (Hydroxytyrosol), folic acid	Yes	1	Capsules	N/A	2.85	2.15	Online pharmacy	Italy
Sample 7	RYR, dry extract of artichoke- cinarina (<i>Cynara scolymus</i>), hesperidin, fenugreek seed dry extract, dry extract from curcumin tree	Yes	2	Tablets	72.5	2.9	N/A	Pharmacy	Italy
Sample 8	RYR	Yes	1	Tablets	240	2.4	N/A	Pharmacy	Bulgaria
Sample 9	Monacolin K, cholin, coenzyme Q10	Yes	1	Tablets	N/A	N/A	2.9	Pharmacy	Poland
Sample 10	RYR, olive fruit dry extract (<i>Olea europaea</i> L.), choline, vitamin B6, vitamin B12, vitamin B9	No Registration date was missing	1	Tablets	99.67	N/A	2.99	Online pharmacy	Poland
Sample 11	RYR	No Bulgarian-language label was missing	2	Capsules	1200	N/A	N/A	FSs retailer	USA
Sample 12	RYR, chrome	Yes	2	Capsules	800	N/A	N/A	Online pharmacy	Bulgaria
Sample 13	RYR	No Registration number and date were missing	2	Capsules	1200	N/A	N/A	Online pharmacy	USA
Sample 14	Monacolins, ciagua dry extract, gamma oryzanol, Coenzyme Q10, policosanols, chromium	No Registration number and date were missing	1	Capsules	N/A	2.9	2.2	Pharmacy	Italy
Sample 15	RYR	No Registration number and date were missing	1	Capsules	60	N/A	3	Online FSs retailer	Poland
Sample 16	RYR, <i>Citrus limon</i> Osbeck extract, grape seed extract, L-leucine, vitamin C	Yes	1	Capsules	184.4	N/A	2.94	Online pharmacy	Bulgaria
Sample 17	RYR, amla dry extract, walnut leaf dry extract (<i>Juglans regia</i>), olive fruit dry extract (<i>Olea europaea</i>)	Yes	2	Tablets	67.2	N/A	2.90	Online pharmacy	Belgium
Sample 18	RYR, black garlic bulb powder (<i>Allium sativum</i>)	Yes	1	Capsules	116	N/A	2.90	Online pharmacy	France

^a Required information according to Bulgarian legislation:

The names of the categories of nutrients or substances characterizing the product, or an indication of their nature;

The portion of the product recommended for daily consumption; a warning not to exceed the recommended daily dose;

A statement to the effect that FSs should not be used as a substitute for a varied diet;

A statement that the product should be stored out of the reach of young children; and

The registration number and registration date of the FS as recorded in the national register, in accordance with the Food Act.

Abbreviations: FS, food supplement; N/A, not available; RYR, red yeast rice.

include the mandatory warning to store the product out of reach of young children. One FS (Sample 11) lacked a Bulgarian-language label entirely, omitting all required indications and warnings for Bulgaria and the EU, as well as the registration number and date in the BFS register (Table 1).

In Table 1, a distinction is made between the total RYR content (the raw botanical preparation) and the concentration of monacolins (the restricted active substances). This ensures alignment with the terminology used in Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006, where the 3 mg safety threshold applies to the total monacolin content. The packaging of 15 FSs indicated the RYR content per maximum daily dose (Samples 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, and 18), which ranged from 58 mg (Sample 3) to 1200 mg (Samples 11 and 13). In contrast, two FSs (Samples 6 and 14) reported only the total monacolins content per maximum daily dose. Four FSs (Samples 2, 3, 7, and 8) provided both the RYR and monacolin contents per maximum daily dose. Among the FSs reporting monacolin content, values ranged from 2.4 mg (Samples 2 and 8) to 2.9 mg (Samples 3, 7, and 14) (Table 1).

The monacolin K content per maximum daily dose was specified on the labels of 11 FSs (Samples 1, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10, 14, 15, 16, 17, and 18), ranging from 2.15 mg (Sample 6) to 2.99 mg (Sample 10). One FS (Sample 5) stated that the monacolin K content was below 3 mg, whereas another (Sample 15) indicated a content of 3 mg, exceeding European regulatory limits, which prohibit a daily intake of 3 mg or more of monacolins. The labels of seven FSs did

not specify the monacolin K content per maximum daily dose on the packaging (Samples 2, 3, 7, 8, 11, 12, and 13). Notably, one FS (Sample 9) did not provide either the RYR or total monacolins content but included the monacolin K amount per maximum daily dose (Table 1).

The labels of two FSs (Samples 6 and 14) included information on both total monacolins and monacolin K content per maximum daily dose, whereas three FSs (Samples 11, 12, and 13) indicated only the RYR content per serving, without specifying monacolins or monacolin K (Table 1).

The majority of the analyzed FSs containing RYR featured multicomponent formulations. These were most frequently integrated with coenzyme Q10 and a range of botanical extracts, including artichoke, bergamot, olive fruit dry extract, black garlic, and turmeric rhizome dry extract (curcumin). Furthermore, these FSs commonly incorporated B-complex vitamins, specifically vitamins B6, B9 (folic acid), and B12, alongside other bioactive constituents such as the omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), policosanols, choline, chromium, and hesperidin (Table 1). The labeled indications for these FSs centered on the maintenance of cardiovascular health and lipid homeostasis, with manufacturers primarily emphasizing the optimization of fat metabolism and the regulation of physiological serum cholesterol and triglyceride concentrations.

The 18 selected FSs were evaluated against the specific safety labeling requirements for monacolins from RYR mandated by Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 (Table 2).

Table 2. Information and warnings provided on the label of the analyzed FSs according to Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006.

Sample no.	Information on the Label According to Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006		Warnings on the Label According to Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006			
	The label shall provide the number of individual portions of the product for maximum daily consumption and a warning not to consume a daily amount of 3 mg of monacolins from RYR or more.	The label shall indicate the content of monacolins per portion of the product.	“Should not be consumed by pregnant or lactating women, children below 18 years old and adults above 70 years old”	“Seek advice from a doctor on consumption of this product if you experience any health problems”	“Should not be consumed if you are taking cholesterol-lowering medication”	“Should not be consumed if you are already consuming other products containing RYR”
Sample 1	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 2	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 3	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 4	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 5	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 6	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 7	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 8	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 9	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 10	FC	FC	PC*	FNC	FNC	FNC
Sample 11	FC	FNC	FNC	FNC	FNC	FNC
Sample 12	FNC	FNC	FNC	FNC	FNC	FNC
Sample 13	FNC	FNC	PC*	FNC	FNC	FNC
Sample 14	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 15	FC	FC	FC	FNC	FC	FNC
Sample 16	FC	FC	PC*	FC	FC	FC
Sample 17	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC	FC
Sample 18	FC	FC	PC**	FNC	FC	FC

Note: (FC) Full compliance. All mandatory warnings required by Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 are present.

(PC) Partial compliance. Mandatory warnings are present but incomplete:

* The specific mandatory warning that the FS should not be consumed by adults over 70 years of age was missing.

** The specific mandatory warning that the FS should not be consumed by children below 18 years of age was missing.

(FNC) Full non-compliance. The mandatory information and warnings are entirely absent from the label.

Regulatory compliance was assessed using a traffic-light classification system: full compliance (green), partial compliance (yellow), and full non-compliance (red). While 11 of the 18 FSs were identified as non-compliant regarding the general and specific safety labeling requirements mandated by Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 and Bulgarian legislation, the nature of these deficiencies varied significantly. Several FSs were categorized as “partially compliant” (yellow) because they failed to include some of the specific mandatory warnings for vulnerable age groups (Samples 10, 13, 16, and 18). On the packaging of Sample 10, several mandatory warnings were missing, including that the FS should not be consumed by adults over 70 years of age, that consumers should seek advice from a doctor if health issues arise while using the product, that the FS should not be taken concurrently with cholesterol-lowering medication, and that it should not be consumed together with other products containing RYR. For Sample 11, the Bulgarian-language label was missing, and the English-language label did not meet EU regulatory requirements, resulting in the omission of all required information. The packaging of Sample 12 lacked all warnings applicable to FSs containing monacolins from RYR as restricted substances. Sample 13 was missing multiple required statements, including the monacolins content per serving, the warning against consuming 3 mg or more of monacolins per day, the recommendation to seek advice from a doctor if health issues arise, the age restriction for adults over 70 years, and warnings against concomitant use with cholesterol-lowering medications or other RYR-containing products. On Sample 15, the label did not include the mandatory warning to consult a physician if health problems occur during use or to avoid concurrent use with other RYR products. The packaging of Sample 16 omitted the warning against consumption by adults over 70 years, while Sample 18 lacked warnings indicating that the FS should not be consumed by children under 18 years and that advice from a doctor is necessary if health issues arise during use (Table 2).

Discussion

There is a growing prevalence of FSs on the EU market containing RYR in combination with other active ingredients intended to reduce blood cholesterol levels and support cardiovascular function (Vanhee 2024). Product labeling plays a crucial role in the safe use of FSs by providing information related to product ingredients, directions for use, health and nutrition claims, and safety considerations (Galman 2026). At the same time, regulatory oversight of FSs is often insufficient, and previous studies have demonstrated that the actual content of key ingredients is frequently inaccurately labeled (Petkova 2021; Ivanova 2022; Vanhee 2024). FSs are consumed by individuals of different ages and with varying health conditions, which highlights the importance of pro-

viding appropriate information and warnings on product packaging to ensure safe use (Ivanova 2022).

In the present study, non-compliance with packaging and labeling requirements was identified in eight of the analyzed FSs (Samples 1, 2, 5, 10, 11, 13, 14, and 15). The observed violations included the absence of a registration number and date of entry in the Bulgarian register, illegible labeling, missing mandatory warnings, and, in one case, the complete absence of a Bulgarian-language label containing the required information.

The FSs were also assessed for compliance with European labeling requirements applicable to FSs containing monacolins from RYR. Instances of non-compliance related to the absence of mandatory warnings were identified in seven FSs (Samples 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, and 18), whereas the packaging of the remaining 11 FSs complied with the applicable requirements. In one FS (Sample 12), all labeling requirements applicable to FSs containing monacolins from RYR as a restricted substance were missing. In another FS (Sample 11), both the absence of a Bulgarian-language label and the non-compliance of the English-language label with EU requirements were identified. This FS was manufactured in the United States, where regulatory requirements differ from those applicable within the EU. According to the labeling requirements for FSs containing monacolins from RYR, the content of monacolins per serving must be indicated. This study revealed that this information was missing or incomplete for some of the analyzed FSs (Samples 11, 12, and 13).

Overall, non-compliance with regulatory labeling requirements was identified in 11 (Samples 1, 2, 5, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, and 18) of the 18 FSs examined, due to missing mandatory information required by national legislation or the absence of warnings mandated by European regulations for FSs containing monacolins from RYR. These findings suggest a potential risk to consumer health.

The primary factors affecting consumers' decisions to use FSs are the perceived health benefits and safety considerations. Information on potential health benefits and the associated health claims is typically provided on product labels (Banović Fuentes 2025). Furthermore, the information provided on product labels is essential to ensure that consumers can make informed purchasing decisions and are fully aware of product composition and associated risks (Gabriels 2013).

Other studies have likewise reported deficiencies in the labeling of FSs containing RYR. In a study by Vanhee et al., 35 FSs containing RYR, purchased from an EU e-commerce platform or registered online pharmacies, were assessed for compliance with EU legislation regarding total monacolin K content. Labeling non-compliance was identified in six products, including missing or incomplete mandatory warnings and the absence of information on the total monacolin content (Vanhee 2024).

A study conducted by Galman et al. evaluating 403 FSs containing a variety of ingredients revealed sub-

stantial non-compliance with labeling requirements, most frequently associated with the omission of essential product information, particularly the failure to disclose product composition. Furthermore, the absence of mandatory safety warnings and traceability information within the respective country was also reported (Galman 2026).

According to EFSA, there is considerable variability in both the composition and the monacolin content of FSs. Monacolins derived from red fermented rice are frequently incorporated into multi-ingredient FSs, which have not been sufficiently evaluated, either individually or in combination. Moreover, the safe use of monacolins in certain vulnerable consumer groups cannot be adequately assessed due to the lack of data on the effects of concomitant consumption of RYR FSs with foods or medicinal products that inhibit the CYP3A4 enzyme, which is involved in monacolin metabolism (European Commission 2022).

In light of these uncertainties and the statements provided by stakeholders regarding the safety profile of monacolins from RYR, EFSA has allowed stakeholders to submit data demonstrating the safety of these substances. The European Commission is required to decide within 4 years of the entry into force of Regulation (EU) 2022/860 whether monacolins from RYR should be included in Annex III, Part A, “Prohibited substances,” or remain in Part B, “Restricted substances,” taking into account EFSA’s assessment of all submitted data (European Commission 2022).

On the EU market, FSs increasingly contain combinations of RYR with plant extracts or coenzyme Q10, rather than products based solely on pure RYR powder, to lower blood cholesterol levels (Vanhee 2024). A wide range of additional compounds, including probiotics, are also combined with RYR or its extracts in the formulation of various products. Some of these substances, such as berberine and polyunsaturated fatty acids, have been shown to exert beneficial effects on lipid and glucose metabolism, whereas others, such as coenzyme Q10, are included to mitigate statin-associated adverse effects (Chen 2023).

Further research is necessary to establish clear associations between specific ingredients and the efficacy of RYR. Consequently, both health authorities and consumers should pay closer attention to these issues and minimize the overstatement of the claimed effects of FSs (Chen 2023; Slavcheva 2024).

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that some of the FSs purchased from Bulgarian pharmacies, FS stores, online pharmacies, and online retailers do not comply with European labeling requirements, including those specific to monacolins from RYR under EU legislation. While the analyzed products varied in their chemical declarations, the primary concern remains the lack of mandatory safety warnings. These findings highlight

significant gaps in labeling adequacy and regulatory compliance, which may prevent consumers from making informed safety decisions regarding their daily monacolin intake. Consequently, there is a clear need for strengthened regulatory control of FSs both prior to and after their placement on the market. As these products are not entirely risk-free, consumers must be adequately informed about their composition, appropriate use, and potential health risks.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following: AI was used only for language editing, including grammar and spelling correction

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, K.S. and R.S.; methodology, K.S. and R.S.; software, K.S.; validation, K.S., R.S., and D.K.; formal analysis, K.S., R.S., and D.K.; investigation, K.S. and R.S.; resources, K.S. and D.K.; data curation, K.S. and R.S.; writing—original draft preparation, K.S.; writing—review and editing, R.S. and D.K.; visualization, K.S. and R.S.; supervision, R.S. and D.K.; project administration, K.S., R.S., and D.K.; funding acquisition, K.S., R.S., and D.K.

Author ORCIDs

Katerina Slavcheva <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4127-3385>

Radiana Staynova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8466-3236>

Daniela Kafalova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4105-9485>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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